

Table 1. Summary of measurement of sleep quality and cortisol among healthcare shift workers of the included studies.

Author	Sample size(<i>n</i>)	Exposure of working shift	Cortisol measures	Sleep quality measures	Outcome	Conclusions
Zhang ²⁷ , 2023 (China)	Nurses (n=152)	Type of shift: 8 hours (day-evening-night) & 12 hours (day-night)	Saliva samples were collected between: 7:00-8:00 & 19:00-20:00	Sleep wake indexes analyse by actigraphy data	Compared with the 8-hour shift nurses, the 12-hour shift nurses had: Cortisol result: Higher saliva cortisol levels before the day shift (median 0.54 vs. 0.31, $p < .005$) and after the night shift (median 0.51 vs. 0.31, $p < .005$). Sleep result: Significantly more TST (456 vs. 364 min) Longer reaction time before the night shift (286 vs. 277 min).	Fast rapid rotation in shift workers disturbed circadian rhythm and reduced total sleep time
Vivarelli ²⁰ , 2023 (Italy)	Nurses (n=102)	Type of shift: Night shift with forward rotating shift. Morning shift followed by an afternoon shift and a night shift, then followed by a rest day	Saliva: morning & evening	PSQI & ESS	Cortisol result: 17% had above threshold limit of morning salivary cortisol. 91% had below threshold limit of evening cortisol. Sleep result: PSQI :75% good sleep, 21.6% poor sleep. 2.9% bad sleep. ESS: 85.3% no daytime sleepiness	There was positive relationship between cortisol and sleepiness even not significant

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Minelli²⁸, 2021 (Italy)	Nurses (n=30)	Type of shift: Morning shift 06:00 Afternoon shift 14:00 Night shift 22:00	Saliva: Four salivary samples were collected: - 21:00 -24:00 -03:00 -06:00	PSQI	Cortisol result: Cortisol concentration low around 21:00 and 24:00 then increasing during early morning between 03:00 and 06:00. Cortisol output during the night shift failed to correlate with PSQI score. Cortisol output during night shifts positively correlates with basal cortisol diurnal secretion measured during non-working days. Sleep result: PSQI: 76% had good sleep.	Rotating shift worker showed that low total cortisol during night work associated with circadian misalignment.
Ljevak²⁶, 2022 (Croatia)	Subjects (n=157): 135 female nurses. 22 male medical technicians	Control group: Morning shifts (7:30 to 14:30) Experimental group: 12 working hours to 24 hours off-work & 12 working night shift hours-48 hours off-work	Blood: collected at 7.30a.m.	Standard Shiftwork Index	Cortisol result: 5% of shift workers had morning cortisol levels lower than the reference values, and 5% had morning cortisol levels higher than the reference values. Sleep result: Shift workers showed significantly higher levels of sleep difficulties than the first shift workers. Strong correlation was found in the rate of sleep disturbances between morning shift workers and those participants working a rotating shift system.	Shift workers had impaired cortisol level and higher level of sleep difficulties.

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Bani-Issa²², 2020 (UAE)	Healthy adult women healthcare professionals (n=335)	Day or night shifts	Saliva samples were collected at: (7:00-8:00) & (19:00-20:00)	PSQI	<p>Cortisol result: Morning cortisol level: 36.1% had impaired below average levels. Bedtime cortisol level:14.3% had high bedtime cortisol levels. There was a significant correlation between morning and bedtime cortisol levels (r = 0.196, p = 0.001).</p> <p>Sleep result: 60.3% had poor sleep quality. Morning and bedtime cortisol levels were not significantly correlated with quality of sleep (r = 0.26, p = 0.57 for morning cortisol; r = 0.013, p = 0.92 for bedtime cortisol) .</p>	Shift workers had impaired morning and bedtime cortisol level with poor sleep quality. Cortisol levels in the morning and at night were independently correlated with sleep quality.
Tsai²³, 2019 (Taiwan)	Female nurse (n=61)	Worked 8 hour per shift. 4 weeks of regular day-shift work (8:00–16:00)	4 saliva samples collected at: awakening and after awakening 0 min, 30 min, 6 hours, 12 hour.	PSQI Actigraphy data	<p>Cortisol result: LSQ had a higher cortisol concentration at awakening (0 min) than did the HSQ. LSQ had a flatter CAR and smaller diurnal cortisol slope 30 minutes to 12 hours than HSQ. HSQ had significantly higher cortisol concentration at 30 minutes after awakening (11.79 + 5.80 ng/mL) than LSQ. HSQ had significantly lower mean cortisol concentration at 12 hours after awakening (2.40 + 2.48 ng/ml) than LSQ.</p> <p>Sleep result: 54.3% LSQ (CPSQI > 5), 45.7% HSQ (CPSQI ≤ 5), HSQ had greater TST, higher SE, and shorter WASO and SOL than the LSQ.</p>	Low sleep quality showed flatter cortisol awakening response (CAR).

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Chang²⁴, 2018 (Taiwan)	Female nurses (n=128)	Types of shifts: 08:00–16:00 16:00–24:00 00:00–08:00	Saliva: Collected after waking and 30 minutes after waking.	PSQI	Cortisol result: CARi night shift and the evening shift workers is significantly lower than the day shift. Shift type significantly influenced CARi (F = 19.66, p < 0.001). Sleep result: Evening shift or the night shift workers have significantly poorer sleep quality than those working the day shift. Shift type significantly influenced sleep quality (F = 15.13, p < 0.001).	There was significantly correlated between CARi and sleep quality; nurses with higher CARi had better sleep quality.
Lowson²¹, 2013 (UK)	Nurses (n=20)	Type shifts: Nurses (n=15) 7 to 8 hour and night shifts of 10 to 12 hour, 07.00 to 21.30 h and finishing between 07.00 to 08.00. Nurses (n=5) 12 h shifts with shift changes 20:00 and 08:00	Saliva: Collected just after waking in the morning and just before sleeping in the evening	PSQI	Cortisol result: Cortisol level soon after waking significantly lower (time 07:58±38 min) (12.5±5.6 nmol/L) (p < 0.001) than the late evening 21:53±1 h 17 min) 4.0±5.2 nmol/L During periods of night work: The early morning cortisol levels for nurses was 10.7±5.7 nmol/L which was significantly lower (p < 0.05) than the early morning cortisol level (14.2±5.0 nmol/L) for other times the early morning saliva samples were collected significantly later (p < 0.01) compared with other mornings (08:16±34 min) following night shifts compared with 07:41±34 min for other mornings). For late evening cortisol levels, higher cortisol levels (4.9±7.2 nmol/L) during periods of night work (non-significant) (p = 0.102) of compared with other times (3.0 ±1.5 nmol/L). Sleep result: During periods of night work, sleep quality worse (nonsignificant) and more sleepiness (Karolinska Sleepiness Scale) before (p < 0.01) and after (p < 0.001) their main period of day sleep compared with night-time sleep-in periods of no night work.	Night shift workers reported to have worse sleep quality (non-significant) and lower early morning cortisol level than other mornings.

Abbreviations: Cortisol levels (CARI); Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (PSQI); Epworth Sleepiness Scale (ESS); cortisol awakening response (CAR); Low sleep quality (LSQ); High sleep quality (HSQ); Chinese version of the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index (CPSQI); Total sleep time (TST); Sleep efficiency (SE); Wake after sleep onset (WASO); Sleep onset latency (SOL)